

EXPERIMENTAL AND FEM COMPACT TENSION TEST FOR FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF 3D-PRINTED HYDROXYAPATITE

Leire Viana Uribe (1), Maria E. Pianou (2), Francesco Baino (2), Luca D'Andrea (1), Pasquale Vena (1)

1. Department of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Italy

2. Institute of Materials Physics and Engineering, Applied Science and Technology Department, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

Introduction

Bone scaffolds offer a promising solution for treating critical-size bone defects, with bioceramics like Hydroxyapatite (HA) playing a pivotal role in tissue regeneration due to their biocompatibility and bioactivity. However, HA's inherent brittleness has limited its clinical use, emphasizing the need to study its fracture mechanics [1]. Understanding the intrinsic fracture toughness is of primary importance when evaluating the biomechanical performance of a scaffold in specific load-bearing anatomical sites. In particular, material characterization on samples produced with the same technology and featuring the same characteristic size is essential for ensuring reliable performance. This study employs a combined experimental-FEM approach on Compact Tension (CT) tests to evaluate the fracture toughness of miniaturized 3D-Printed HA samples, designed to match the size of real bone scaffolds and bring the analysis closer to clinical applications.

Methods

Twenty miniaturized V-shaped CT samples (Figure 1A) were produced by Vat Photopolymerization and subjected to tensile force. A 5N load cell measured the maximum force (F) at failure. The fracture surface area (SA) was analyzed via confocal laser scanning, revealing spherical voids cut by the fracture. To complement the experimental study, a phase-field method in FEM was used, which balances accuracy and efficiency to characterize the macroscopic strength and toughness of ceramic scaffolds [2]. The HA specimen was modeled as elastic ($E = 100 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.33$) [3]. Parameters like fracture toughness (G_c), phase-field length scale (l), and mesh density were varied to assess their influence on fracture behavior. An upper bound of the energy release rate (G_c) was estimated as:

$$G_c = \frac{1}{2 \cdot SA} \cdot F^2 \cdot C \quad (1)$$

where C is the compliance estimated through FEM.

Results

The average F was $4.46 \text{ N} \pm 0.5 \text{ N}$, with a SA of $2.48 \text{ mm}^2 \pm 1.17 \text{ mm}^2$. Void dimensions ($\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$) (Figure 1C) aligned with previous findings, indicating 0.35% microporosity. FEM simulations tracked crack propagation (Figure 1B) and estimated stress concentrations (σ_{22}) at crack initiation. Force-displacement curves revealed the material's tensile response. The agreement between experimental and FEM forces enabled the estimation of G_c between

0.0004-0.0016 N/mm, emphasizing the impact of mechanical and geometrical factors in fracture toughness. Especially, the spherical voids contributed to early failure of the samples.

Figure 1: A) 3D-Printed HA samples at real scale, and B) Spatial and temporal evolution of crack propagation, shown before (left) and after (right) fracture, C) Microscope image highlighting spherical voids on the fracture surface.

Discussion

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of a combined experimental-FEM approach in characterizing the fracture behavior of miniaturized 3D-printed HA scaffolds. Experimental tests alone are limited in capturing displacement, and stress concentrations at crack initiation, whereas FEM modelling allows for a more comprehensive analysis. By incorporating voids into the simulations, we showed their significant impact on fracture toughness, emphasizing the need for models that account for these microstructural features. Ongoing nanoindentation tests aim to validate FE findings. This approach enhances the accuracy and reliability of fracture predictions, providing essential insights for the design of tailored bone substitutes with improved mechanical performance.

References

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